

Theoretical studies on the thermal decomposition of fluoromethanethiol (CH₂FSH)

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All species involved in the decomposition of CH₂FSH and CH₃FS have been investigated using density functional theory (DFT). The molecular geometries for various species are optimized employing B3LYP method implementing 6-311++G** basis sets. The potential energy surface is drawn out for this reaction. The vibrational mode analysis is used to elucidate the relationships of the intermediates, transition states and the products. The extensive investigation shows that the reaction mechanism is reliable and the HF + CH₂S are the main products.

Many important reactions in combustion and atmospheric chemistry, especially in relation to environmental SO_x issues¹, involve sulfur atoms and sulfur-containing species, so the study of sulfur atom should attract our interests. The reaction of S (¹D) with methane has been reported to follow an insertion/elimination mechanism² as well as that of the reaction between O (¹D) and methane^{3,4}. The unimolecular decomposition of the intermediate methanethiol (CH₃SH) has been studied experimentally and theoretically^{5,6}. Highly energetic halogenated methanols have been found to be intermediates in the insertion reaction of O (¹D) with halogenated methanes (e.g. CH₃F, CHF₃, CHCl₃)^{7,8}. Fluorinated methanethiol (CH₂FSH) may be the activated intermediate in the insertion reaction of S (¹D) with CH₃F, so CH₂FSH may be also formed in other important reactions, such as CH₂ + HSF, CHF + H₂S, F + CH₂SH and SH + CH₂F. In addition, CH₃SF, which is one of the isomers of CH₂FSH⁹, can be produced by the reaction of F with the key atmospheric sulfur species, dimethylsulfide (DMS). Therefore, it is necessary to study the unimolecular decomposition of CH₂FSH for a further understanding of the atmospheric chemistry of halogenated organic sulfur compounds. Wang¹⁰ has revealed the possible decomposition pathway of CH₂FSH and CH₃SF. Since there is no experimental report on the decomposition of CH₂FSH or CH₃SF, a *priori* theoretical prediction is appropriate. In this paper, we will use the vibrational modes analysis to elucidate the relationships of the transition states, intermediates and the product, and explain on the reaction mechanism in detail.

Recently, the analysis of the vibrational mode and the

vibrational frequencies for the transition states and the intermediates has attracted the attention of Mann and McGrivern for the S_N² reaction of Cl⁻ + CH₃Cl¹¹ and the calculation of the dissociation energy of C-H and C-X¹², respectively. And the elucidation of reaction mechanisms via vibrational mode analysis gets more attention^{13,14}. All multi-atom molecules can produce an infrared spectrum because of the rotation and vibration of atom groups. The characteristics of the normal mode vibrations are that all atoms reach their equilibrium points at the same time and come to the maximum simultaneously when vibrating, but the center of mass remains unchangeable and the molecule as a whole does not rotate. If *n* is the atom number, for non-linear molecules there are (3*n*-6) normal vibration modes and for linear molecules there are (3*n*-5). In a sense, the numerical values of the frequencies of a molecule can reflect the reaction potential barrier, namely the actual activation energy. If a bond is extended or weakened, the frequencies are red-shifted; on the contrary, if the bond is shortened and strengthened, the frequencies are blue-shifted. So the changes of the vibrational frequencies and vibrational modes must be relative to the transformations of the structures.

Computations :

The optimizations of the reactant, intermediate transition states (TS) and products are performed with GAUSS- IAN 98 programs package¹⁵ at the B3LYP/6-311++G** level. The popular hybrid density functional B3LYP method, namely Beck's¹⁶ three-parameter non-local exchange functional with the non-local correlation functional

Table 1. Vibrational frequencies and their vibrational mode assignment for the reactants and products involved in the decomposition of CH₂FSH

Species	Frequency	Mode assignment	Species	Frequency	Mode assignment		
CH ₂	1385	CH ₂ scissors	HSF	732	F-S stretch		
	2899	CH ₂ symmetric stretch		998	H-S rock in plane		
	2965	CH ₂ asymmetric stretch		2640	H-S stretch		
SF	773	SF stretch	HF	4099	H-F stretch rock out of plane		
CH ₃	537	CH ₃ rock out of plane	CH ₂ S	1010	H ₁ -C-H ₂ rock in plane		
	1402	H ₂ -C-H ₃ scissors		1028	H ₂ -C-H ₂ rock out of plane		
	1403	H ₂ -C-H ₃ scissors		1083	C-S stretch		
	3103	CH ₃ symmetric stretch		1497	H ₁ -C-H ₂ scissors		
	3282	H ₁ -C-H ₂ asymmetric stretch		3058	H ₃ -C-H ₂ symmetric stretch		
	3283	H ₁ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		3142	H ₃ -C-H ₂ asymmetric stretch		
CH ₃ S	580	CH ₃ twist	CH ₃ F	1033	F-H-stretch		
	706	C-S stretch		1183	CH ₃ rock out of plane		
	869	H ₁ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane		1184	CH ₃ deform		
	1343	CH ₃ umbrella		1479	CH ₃ umbrella		
	1369	H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock in plane		1487	CH ₃ scissors		
	1470	C ₂ -C-H ₃ rock in plane		1488	CH ₃ twist		
	3072	CH ₃ symmetric stretch		3031	CH ₃ symmetric stretch		
	3083	CH ₃ asymmetric stretch		3114	CH ₃ asymmetric stretch		
	3107	C ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		3118	CH ₂ asymmetric stretch		
	CH ₂ SFH	294		H-S rock	CH ₃ SF	194	CH ₃ rock in plane
		373		S-F-C bend in plane		282	C-S-F bend in plane
		711		C-S stretch		688	C-S-F stretch
		805		H ₁ -S rock + H ₂ -H ₃ rock in plane		714	C-S-F asymmetric stretch
		987		C-F stretch		975	CH ₃ rock out of plane
1070		H ₁ -S-C bend in plane	985	CH ₂ rock in plane			
1260		H ₂ -C-H ₃ twist	1355	CH ₃ umbrella			
1358		H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane	1437	CH ₃ twist			
1472		H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock in plane	1478	CH ₂ scissors			
2668		H ₁ -S stretch	3030	CH ₃ symmetric stretch			
3075		H ₂ -C-H ₃ symmetric stretch	3110	CH ₃ asymmetric stretch			
3141		H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch	3134	CH ₂ asymmetric stretch			
HSCH		449	H ₁ -S rock	FCSH		417	H-S-C-F bend in plane
		812	C-S stretch			550	H-S rock out of plane
	882	H ₂ -C rock	685		S-C stretch		
	921	S-C-H bend in plane	902		H-S rock in plane		
	2513	H ₂ -S stretch	1102		F-C stretch		
	3150	H ₂ -C stretch	2540		H-S stretch		
	4416	H-H stretch	2654		H-S stretch		
CHFS	471	S-C-F bend in plane	HCSF	287	C-S-F bend in plane		
	890	C-H rock out of plane		497	H-C-S bend in plane		
	980	C-F stretch		614	H-C rock in plane		
	1177	C-S stretch		829	H-C rock out of plane		
	1369	C-H rock in plane		1315	C-S stretch		
	3146	C-H stretch		3291	H-C stretch		
CH ₂ SH	19	H ₂ -C-S-H ₁ twist	CH ₂ FS	382	F-C-S bend in plane		
	337	H ₃ -C-S-H ₂ rock out of plane		728	C-S stretch		
	783	H ₂ -C-S-H ₁ bend in plane		751	H ₁ -C-H ₂ rock in plane		
	834	C-S stretch		984	C-F stretch		
	1075	CH ₂ -S-H ₁ rock in plane		1191	H ₂ -C-H ₁ twist		
	1409	H ₃ -C-H ₂ scissors		1320	H ₁ -C-H ₂ rock out of plane		
	2674	H ₁ -S stretch		1418	H ₁ -C-H ₂ scissors		
	3172	H ₂ -C-H ₃ symmetric stretch		3019	H ₁ -C-H ₂ symmetric stretch		
	3304	H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		3065	H ₂ -C-H ₁ asymmetric stretch		

of Lee *et al.*¹⁷, is used throughout the study. Subsequently, connections of the transition states and products are confirmed by intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) calculation^{18–20}. All relative energies discussed below are electronic and zero-point energy corrected. The number of imaginary frequencies (0 or 1) confirms a local minimum or a transition state.

Results and discussion

The geometries of the reactants, intermediates, transition states and products involved in the decomposition of CH₂FSH are shown in Fig. 1. The schematic potential energy profile is depicted in Fig. 2. The vibrational frequencies and the vibrational mode assignment of the reactants and products are listed in Table 1. The vibrational frequen-

Table 2. Vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode assignment for TS2, TS3, TS4, TS5, TS6 and TS7

Species	Frequency	Frequency assignment	Species	Frequency	Frequency assignment		
TS2	i228	H ₂ -C stretch	TS3	i996	H ₃ -F stretch		
	83	S-H ₂ -C bend in plane		162	F-C-S bend in plane		
	169	H ₁ -S rock		331	H ₂ -C-S-H ₁ rock out of plane		
	214	S-H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane		574	H ₁ -S rock		
	325	H ₁ -S-H ₂ twist		794	H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock + H ₁ -S rock		
	573	H ₃ -C rock out of plane		939	H ₂ -C-SH ₁ twist		
	1142	C-F stretch		949	C-S stretch		
	1211	H ₁ -S-H ₂ rock in plane		1133	H ₂ -C-S-H ₁ rock in plane		
	1419	H ₃ -C rock in plane		1361	H ₃ -C-H ₂ scissors		
	2439	H ₂ -S stretch		2098	C-H ₃ -F twist		
	2681	H ₁ -S stretch		2564	H ₁ -S stretch		
	2846	H ₃ -C stretch		3175	H ₁ -S stretch		
	TS4	i1132		H ₂ -C-H ₃ bend in plane	TS5	i1157	H ₁ -F stretch
		373		F-C-S-H ₁ bend out of plane		462	F-C-S bend in plane
439		H ₁ -S rock out of plane	521	H ₁ -F rock out of plane			
546		H ₂ -C-S-H ₁ twist	585	C-F stretch			
665		H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock	854	C-S stretch			
730		H ₂ -C rock	860	H ₃ -C-H ₂ twist			
1071		H ₁ -S rock in plane	955	H ₃ -C-H ₂ rock in plane			
1162		H ₂ -C-H ₃ twist	1212	H ₃ -C-H ₂ rock out of plane			
1640		H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch	1465	H ₃ -C-H ₂ scissors			
2386		H ₂ -H ₃ stretch	1534	F-H ₁ -S twist			
2568		S-H ₁ stretch	3102	H ₃ -C-H ₂ symmetric stretch			
TS6	i1582	H ₁ -H ₂ stretch	TS7	3197	H ₃ -C-H ₂ asymmetric stretch		
	391	S-C-F bend in plane		i1147	S-H ₁ -C rock in plane		
	721	H ₁ -H ₂ rock out of plane		241	C-S-F bend in plane		
	768	F-C-S twist		458	CH ₃ rock in plane		
	858	S-C stretch		458	F-S-CH ₂ rock		
	910	H ₂ -C rock		530	H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane		
	1005	C-F stretch		881	H ₃ -C-S bend in plane		
	1279	H ₃ -C rock in plane		981	H ₂ -C-S bend in plane		
	1371	H ₃ -C-H ₂ scissors		1155	C-H-S twist		
	1830	H ₂ -H ₁ -S twist		1495	H ₂ -C-H ₃ scissors		
	2258	H ₁ -H ₂ -C bend in plane		2006	H ₁ -S stretch		
	3097	H ₃ -C stretch		3091	H ₂ -C-H ₃ symmetric stretch		
				3207	H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		

cies and the vibrational mode assignment of all the transition states and intermediates are listed in Table 2 and Table 3.

Vibrational mode analysis for the reactants and products :

The reactant of CH₂FSH belongs to the group point of C₁. Since CH₂FSH has 14 possible pathways, there are 24 products. H₂, HF, FS and HS are all linear, they have only a stretch mode. CHF, HSF have three frequencies, because the C-H and C-F; S-H and S-F has an angle of 101.8°, 100.6° respectively. The products of H₂S, CH₂S, CH₂F, CH₃ should be assigned to the C_{2v} group and the two hydrogen atoms always vibrate simultaneously. HCSF, FCSH, CHFS, HCSH belongs to the C_s group, because the D(HCSF), D(FCSH), D(SCHF), D(HSCH) are 0°, 0°, 0°, 180° respectively. The products of CH₃S, CH₃F, belong to the group point of C_s, as Table 1 shows for the CH₃ atomic group has no degenerate vibrational modes. CH₂FS should assign to the C_s group, for the two hydrogen atoms always

vibrate simultaneously. CH₂SH belong to the C₁ group, for the distances of C-H₁ are different slightly.

Vibrational mode analysis for the decomposition of CH₂FSH :

There are 14 reaction channels involves in the decomposition of CH₂FSH, and they can be described as :

The oscillation frequencies and their vibrational mode assignment of TS2, TS3, TS4, TS5, TS6 and TS7 are listed in

Table 3. Vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode assignment for TS8, TS9, IM1 and IM1'

Species	Frequency	Frequency assignment	Species	Frequency	Frequency assignment		
TS8	i1902	H-F stretch	TS9	i1100	H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		
	407	F-S-C bend in plane		275	F-S-C bend in plane		
	493	H-F-S twist		386	CH ₃ rock in plane		
	563	CH ₃ rock in plane		541	F-S stretch		
	912	H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane		611	C-H ₁ rock out of plane		
	955	S-C stretch		691	H ₂ -C-H ₃ rock out of plane		
	1007	H ₂ -CH ₃ rock in plane		877	H ₂ -C-H ₃ twist		
	1143	C-H rock out of plane		1064	S-C-H ₁ bend in plane		
	1458	CH ₃ umbrella		1098	CH ₃ twist		
	1510	C-H rock in plane		1370	H ₂ -C-H ₃ scissors		
	3086	H ₂ -C-H ₃ symmetric stretch		3154	H ₂ -H ₃ stretch		
	3187	H ₂ -C-H ₃ asymmetric stretch		3251	H ₁ -C stretch		
	CH ₃ SF (IM1)	194		CH ₃ rock in plane	<i>cis</i> -CH ₃ SF (IM1')	190	CH ₃ rock in plane
		282		C-S-F bend in plane		317	C-S-F bend in plane
		688		C-S stretch		696	S-F stretch
714		C-S-F asymmetric stretch	704	C-S stretch			
975		CH ₃ rock out of plane	942	CH ₃ rock out of plane			
985		CH ₂ rock in plane	983	CH ₂ rock in plane			
1355		CH ₃ umbrella	1349	CH ₃ umbrella			
1437		CH ₃ twist	1448	CH ₃ twist			
1478		CH ₂ scissors	1479	CH ₂ scissors			
3030		CH ₃ symmetric stretch	3042	CH ₃ symmetric stretch			
3110		CH ₃ asymmetric stretch	3130	CH ₂ asymmetric stretch			
3134		CH ₂ asymmetric stretch	3133	CH ₃ asymmetric stretch			

Table 2. The CF, SH and CS bond cleavages of CH₂FSH produce F + CH₂SH, H + CH₂FS and CH₂F + SH, respectively. These types of decomposition reactions proceed without any transition state since their reverse reactions are highly reactive radical-radical association processes. The bond dissociation energies were calculated to be 443.2, 343.7, 281.2 kJ mol⁻¹ at the B3LYP level, respectively. The decomposition pathways of CH₂FSH to S (¹D) + CH₃F and CH₂ + HSF are followed the insertion mechanism. The product channel CH₂ + HSF is energetically the most unfavorable because of its endothermicity of 469.4 kJ mol⁻¹.

The H₂ atom CH₂FSH migrates from C to S, forming H₂S + CHF via transition state TS2. For TS2, the imaginary frequency is assigned to the H₂-C stretching mode (i228 cm⁻¹), the imaginary frequency always is relative to the bond that is forming or the bond that is rupturing, in this case the imaginary frequency means that the H₂-C is unstable. Fig. 1 also shows that the H₂-C bond has been elongated to about 2.005 Å, which is longer than the normal length of the H-C bond. Two H₁-S-H₂ modes, H₂-S, S-H₂-C show the formation of H₂-S bond. The S-H₂-C bend in plane, H₂-S stretch, H₁-S-H₂ twist, H₁-S-H₂ rock in plane shows that the migrating hydrogen atom has already added to the sulfur; at the same time, the H₂-C stretching mode, which is imaginary frequency, at i228 cm⁻¹ denote that this atom has not completely migrated from carbon atom.

There are two three-center product channels in the decomposition of CH₂FSH, forming HF + CHSH and H₂ + FCSH via transition states TS3 and TS4, respectively. In

TS3, the imaginary frequency is the H₃-F stretching mode (i996.5 cm⁻¹) proves that the formation of H₃-F bond. The S-C-F bend in plane mode red-shift to 162 cm⁻¹ show that the C-F bond is weakened; and the H₂-C-H₃ rock mode red-shifted to 574 cm⁻¹ may imply that the C-H₃ is weakened too. In fact, the breaking C-H₃ bond is extended to 1.199 Å, and the distance of C-F bond is extended to 2.202 Å. But the C-S stretching mode blue-shifted 949 cm⁻¹ may show that the C-S bond is strengthened. For TS4, the H₂-C-H₃ bend in plane mode at i1132 cm⁻¹, which is imaginary frequency, with the decrement of the H₂-C-H₃ rock mode denotes the C-H₂ and C-H₃ are extended. Fig. 1 shows the C-H₃ bond is 1.256 Å by length, and the distance of C-H₂ bond is extended to 1.750 Å. The appearance of the H₂-H₃ stretching mode at 238 cm⁻¹ shows that the formation of the H-H bond. Furthermore, the large imaginary frequency may imply a high potential barrier. Fig. 2 testifies that the internal energy of TS4 is as large as 372.0 kJ cm⁻¹.

It is noted that CH₂FSH can undergo elimination of H or H₂ through other pathways. The 1,2-HF elimination of CH₂FSH leads to HF and CH₂S via transition state TS5, and the 1,2-HH elimination forms H₂ and CHFS via TS6. Both TS5 and TS6 are four-center transition states. For TS5, the H₁-F stretching mode at i1557 cm⁻¹, which is imaginary frequency, the H₁-F rock out of plane, and the F-H₁-S twist may indicate the formation of the HF. The C-F stretching mode red-shifted to 585 cm⁻¹ may show that the C-F bond is weakened. As shown in Fig. 1, TS5 has C_s symmetry. As to TS6, the imaginary frequency belongs to the H₁-H₂

Fig. 1. The optimized structures for various species involved in the unimolecular decomposition of CH₂FSH and CH₃SF at the B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level. Bond distances are in Å and bond angles are in degrees.

stretching mode ($\nu_{1582} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which means that the H1-H2 bond is forming, and the H1, H2 will eliminate from CH₂FSH. But the appearance of the H1-H2-C bend in plane mode ($\nu_{2258} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the H1-H2-S bend in plane mode

($\nu_{1830} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) show that the C-H2 bond and the S-H1 bond still exist, and the H2 atom has not leave the C atom completely, and the H1 atom has not leave the S atom completely. Compared with the geometric parameters of the

Fig. 2. The overall profile of the potential energy surface for the unimolecular decomposition of CH_2FSH and CH_3SF , the energy were calculated at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level.

three-center transition state structures (TS3 and TS4), the forming HF bond in TS5 are somewhat shorter and the HH bond in TS6 is somewhat longer. In addition, both TS5 and TS6 have lower energies. The barrier heights were calculated to be 190.3 and 341.6 kJ mol^{-1} .

CH_2FSH rearranges to CH_3FS (IM1) via transition state TS7. In TS7, the imaginary frequency is assigned to the S-H1-C rock in plane mode ($i1147 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which means that the H1-S is weakened, and the H1 atom will migrate to the C atom. The emergences of the C-H1-S twist mode (1155 cm^{-1}) and the CH_3 rock in plane mode (458 cm^{-1}) prove the formation of C-H1 bond. In addition, the H1-S stretch red-shifted to 2006 cm^{-1} also indicates that the H1-S is weakened. The appearances of the C-F-S bend in plane mode (241 cm^{-1}) and the F-S- CH_2 rock mode (458 cm^{-1}) show that the S-F has formed. With the rupture of the H1-S bond and C-F bond, CH_3FS will form.

Vibrational mode analysis for the reactions channels of IM1 :

The two configurations of IM1 involves four reaction channels, which can be described as :

The oscillation frequencies and their vibrational mode assignment of TS8, TS9, IM1 and IM1' are listed in Table 2. Two simple bond cleavage pathways of CH_3FS are CS bond scission mode leading to $\text{CH}_3 + \text{SF}$ and the SF bond scission mode leading to $\text{F} + \text{CH}_3\text{S}$. No transition states were found for both paths. At the B3LYP level, the CS and SF bond dissociation energies are 342.6, 377.6 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively.

Two intramolecular elimination channels of CH_3FS were also examined. One is the 1,2-HF elimination via the four-center transition-state TS8, forming $\text{HF} + \text{CH}_2\text{S}$. The other is 1,1-HH elimination via the three-center transition state TS9, forming $\text{H}_2 + \text{HCSF}$. It is interesting that both reactions proceed via *cis-CH}_3\text{FS} structure.*

For TS8, the imaginary frequency is assigned to H-F stretch at $i1902 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which means the formation of H-F, and the appearances of the H-F-S also shows the formation of H-F. The disappearance of the S-F stretching mode, the H-F-S twist mode and the increment of F-S-C bend in plane mode and the S-C stretch mode to 493, 955 cm^{-1} , respectively, mean that the S-F bond is weakened and the C-S is reinforced. The two CH_3 modes indicate that the C-H1 bond has not broken completely. As Fig. 1 shows, the breaking S-F bond is extended to 2.076 Å. With the rupture of the C-H1 bond and the S-F bond, the final product $\text{HF} + \text{CH}_2\text{S}$ will form. The large imaginary frequency indicates a high energy barrier, and the calculated energy is 248.88 kJ mol^{-1} at the B3LYP level. In TS9, the H2-C-H3 asymmetric stretching mode at $i1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is imaginary frequency, may show that the C-H2 bond and the C-H3 bond are weakened. The other three H2-C-H3 modes prove the C-H2 bond and C-H3 bond have not broken completely. In fact, the C-H2 bond and C-H3 bond have been elongated to about 1.408 Å and 1.458 Å, which is longer than the normal length of the C-H bond. In addition, the appearance of H2-H3 stretching mode at 1376 cm^{-1} indicates that the H2-H3 is forming, and the distance of H2-H3 is 0.809 Å. The internal energy of TS9 was calculated to be 3581 kJ mol^{-1} .

In conclusion, on the grounds of computed results from the GAUSSIAN 98 programs package at the B3LYP/6-311++G** level, the unimolecular decomposition mechanism of CH_2FSH and CH_3FS have been investigated thoroughly via the vibrational model analysis. For both mole-

cules, the most favorable channel is the formation of HF + CH₃S via four-center elimination mechanism because of its lowest internal energy (200.4 kJ mol⁻¹) so the main reaction channel involving this system should be CH₃FSH → TS5 → HF + CH₃S and CH₃FSH → TS7 → CH₃SF (IM1) → *cis*-CH₃FS (IM1') → TS9 → H₂ + HCSF.

And the relationships among the reactants, 9 transition states, 2 intermediates and various products involved this multi-channel reaction are elucidated. The vibrational mode analysis shows that the reaction mechanism is reliable.

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